

Case Report

Imatinib Induced Bullous Pemphigoid as a Late Toxicity: A possible Need for Post Treatment Follow-Up?

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Abstract

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The novel use of Tyrosine Kinase Inhibitors (TKI's) has shown to be a major breakthrough in the treatment of Chronic Myeloid Leukemia (CML). It has opened the doors for TKIs use in a series of neoplasms with success rates previously unheard of. Nevertheless, its use is not free of adverse effects. Skin, gastro-intestinal and central nervous systems are the most affected, among which autoimmune response can be observed with a higher incidence in treated populations. Here we report the case of a patient who presented a rare autoimmune disease, bullous pemphigoid, which wasn't described before as one of the adverse effects (early or late), most probably as a therapy-related adverse effect two years after stopping Imatinib® treatment.

Keywords: Chronic Myeloid Leukemia (CML), Tyrosine Kinase Inhibitors (TKI's), Bullous Pemphigoid (BP), Imatinib

INTRODUCTION

Chronic Myeloid Leukemia (CML) is a disease that accounts for approximately 15% of the adult leukemias and is characterized by genetic translocation of chromosomes 9 and 22 (derivative (q34; q11) (Philadelphia chromosome; Ph1). The most frequent symptoms and signs include night sweats, anemia and fatigue. As for laboratory parameters, absolute leukocytosis with a left shift and absolute basophilia and eosinophilia (90% of cases) are among the hematological characteristics of this disease. CML patients can be found in one of three phases of disease: chronic phase, accelerated phase and blastic phase. Most patients (85%) will be diagnosed in the chronic phase (Quintás-Cardama and Cortes, 2006; Thompson et al., 2015).

The tyrosine kinase inhibitors (TKI's) were first approved by the Food and Drug Administration (FDA) in 2001 when Imatinib® entered the market for CML treatment. Their mechanism of action is based mainly in the inhibition of specific trans-membrane tyrosine kinase peptide receptors (blockage of domain trans-activation and subsequent target protein phosphorylation). This blockage results in the inhibition of the activity of CML's fusion product (BCR/ABL), better known as the Philadelphia chromosome. Several studies have shown improvement in results while treating with a TKI, with reported long-term progression of both free disease progression and overall survival (Thompson et al., 2015; Chrobák and Voglová, 2019).

Table 1. Patient's Complete Blood Count (CBC) and Chemistry.

Parameter	Lab Reference	Result
WBC (10 ³ cells/ul)	4.8-10.8	75
Eosinophil's	1-3%	5.3%
Basophils	0-1.5%	6.8%
Blasts	%	0.73
Platelets (10 ³ /ul)	130-400	173
Hemoglobin (g/dL)	14-18	8.9
LDH (U/L)	150-480	1373
ALT (U/L)	0-41	156
GGT (U/L)	0-49	295
AST (U/L)	0-37	76
Total Bilirubin (mg/dL)	0-1.1	3.4

Nevertheless, this treatment is not free of adverse effects. A number of studies have shown cutaneous side effects, among others. Skin toxicity has been reported to occur in 11-67% of the patients, but up to date, no report of Bullous Pemphigoid (BP) has been found in literature (Sood et al., 2018; Valeyrie et al., 2003), reason why we've decided to report this uncommon adverse effect.

BP is a rare autoimmune blistering urticarial disease that most commonly arises in older people. It is characterized by sub-epithelial blister formation with deposition of immunoglobulins and complement within the epidermal and/or mucosal basement membrane zone. The classical lesion is a 1 to 3 cm tense bulla on an erythematous, urticarial, or non-inflammatory base. The trunk, extremity flexures, and axillary and inguinal folds are common sites for cutaneous involvement. For diagnosis, hematoxylin and eosin (H&E) staining in a skin biopsy from a blister, and direct immunofluorescence (DIF) are performed. DIF is considered the most sensitive test for the diagnosis of bullous pemphigoid. Linear IgG and/or linear C3 staining along the basement membrane zone is present in greater than 90 percent of cases, while less intense linear basement membrane zone staining for IgM, IgA and/or IgE may be present (Kershenovich et al., 2014).

As shown in the pioneering Stop Imatinib® trial (STIM1), in patients with Ph1-positive leukemias, the use of Imatinib is associated with a high rate of adverse cutaneous reactions (Etienne et al., 2016).

Moreover, it is thought that the reduction or full stop of TKIs leads to (re)activation of the immune effector response, thereby enhancing autoimmune responses.

To the best of our knowledge this is the first case report of serious BP that occurs as a delayed toxicity after stopping TKI's.

Case story

A 61 year old man with a medical history of hypertension and no other diseases (per medical history and hospital

files), arrived at the emergency room (ER) in September 2004, due to jaundice. Complete blood count showed leukocytosis with eosinophilia and basophilia, but also blood chemistry revealed increased liver enzymes (Table 1). The spleen was enlarged to a span of 16cm.

Bone marrow biopsy (BMB), that showed:

*packed marrow

*myeloid hyperplasia with complete range of maturation

*myeloproliferative disorder, most consistent with chronic myelocytic leukemia.

Cytogenetic analysis showed chromosomal translocation (karyotype): 46,XY,t(9;22)(q34;q11) Philadelphia Chromosome.

FISH test showed translocation of BCR/ABL in 55% of cells and 80% of the cells without third signal, the PCR for BCR/ABL translocation was positive, thereby confirming the diagnosis of CML.

He started treatment with Imatinib® 400mg once daily. After 3 months of treatment the blood count improved but did not achieve complete hematologic remission. After 6 months of treatment the karyotype was 46 XY with no translocation, but the FISH was still positive in 27% of cells for BCR/ABL, partial response was achieved.

Due to this, the dosage was increased to 400mg twice daily.

The cytogenetic results after 20 months of treatment showed complete cytogenetic response and non-detectable disease by PCR, thereby being cured of any measurable disease.

In October 2005 Imatinib® was stopped due to cholelithiasis (a cholecystectomy was performed) and subsequently the patient refused to continue treatment.

In April 2007 the patient relapsed with a blood count showing leukocytosis of 99x10³/μl. Treatment with Imatinib® 400mg twice daily was resumed.

A year later the patient once again achieved complete remission. From June 2008 up until July 2013, the patient received Imatinib® 400mg twice daily. Blood counts and chemistries were normal and qPCR from peripheral blood was negative for BCR/ABL.

In August 2013 due to renal dysfunction the dose was

Table 2. Patient's histological result that confirmed Bullous Pemphigoid That was Diagnostic evaluation through DIF revealed

IgG	positive shining +2 - linearly in the region of the basal membrane
IgA	positive shining +1 - linearly in the region of the basal membrane
IgM	negative
C3	positive shining +4 - linearly in the region of the basal membrane
Fibrinogen	positive shining +2 - Linearly in the region of the basal membrane

reduced to 400 mg once daily.

In April 2017 the drug was stopped due to worsening renal failure as well as a cerebrovascular accident (CVA with left sided hemiplegia), diarrhea and weakness.

In April 2019, 2 years after stopping Imatinib®, the patient was admitted to the hospital due to rapidly developing and bursting blisters on his chest, back, right elbow, right forearm and lower limbs. The biopsy from a blister on the chest revealed the following results, compatible with BP diagnosis.

Histology results:

*Sub-epidermal blisters.

*Peri-vascular and interstitial mixed cell inflammatory infiltrate composed of numerous eosinophils, neutrophils and mononuclear cells in the upper dermis.

The histologic findings were consistent with sub-epidermal blister disease.

Diagnostic evaluation through DIF (Table 2).

The patient was discharged on antibiotic treatment with oral doxycycline 100mg twice daily for a month and topical Clobetasol propionate cream 0.05% to the affected areas, twice daily for two weeks.

Two months later he was readmitted to the Internal Medicine department due to a worsening of the blisters and severe itching. A second biopsy was taken and showed similar results but this time instead of sub-epidermal blisters, it showed sub-epidermal separation with signs of re-epithelization. The patient's condition deteriorated and one week after admission he died of sepsis.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

We have described the case of a patient with a rare and serious adverse event secondary to TKI use two years after achieving complete disease response both by clinical and laboratory parameters, most seemingly due to in part repeated use and discontinuation of Imatinib®.

BP is known to be caused by an elevated autoimmune response, usually secondary to specific genetic changes, physical insulting agent or post-infectiously, but not previously described after TKI use.

Fatal BP with CML is uncommon, moreover when it appears after discontinuation of TKIs. Upon literature review of immune related cutaneous reactions caused by Imatinib® we found that most reports include skin rashes, associated mainly with pruritus, dermatitis, erythema

nodosum and vasculitis (Mughal and Schrieber, 2010; Drummond et al., 2003; Aleem, 2009), but not BP.

As showed in STIM1 patients with Ph1-positive leukemias, who were treated with Imatinib® had a high rate of adverse cutaneous reactions (Etienne et al., 2016).

Furthermore, there is consequent reactivation of the immune system in CML patients with good response on TKI's (Hughes et al., 2017). To the best of our knowledge, this is the first case report of a fatal BP in CML after discontinuing treatment with Imatinib®.

Our case report shows that after a long treatment period with TKIs, and especially after retreatment of hematologic malignancies such as CML, dramatic autoimmune diseases can be observed.

We feel the need to emphasize a close follow up and observation for delayed toxicity in patients with CML (and other malignancies) after TKI treatment. This, to our belief, plays a fundamental role especially in the new era of Targeted Therapy, not only with Imatinib® use, rather will all available TKI.

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The following pictures were taken by a microscope from the histopathological slides result that confirmed Bullous Pemphigoid.

